

Argentometric Titrations of Some Halides and Pseudohalides using 7-Hydroxy-8-(phenyl azo)-Naphthalene 1,3-Disulphonic Acid as an Indicator

S. K. GARG, D. C. AGARWAL and G. K. CHATURVEDI

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra

Manuscript received 30 December 1980, revised 10 March 1981, accepted 2 May 1981

7-Hydroxy-8 (phenyl azo) naphthalene 1,3-disulphonic acid has been used as an adsorption indicator in direct or reverse titrations of silver ion with halides and pseudohalides. The dye has also been used in the determination of iodide and bromide in a binary mixture.

A number of azo dyes have been employed as adsorption indicators in argentometry by Mehrotra *et al*¹, Kolthoff² and others³⁻⁴. Recently Agarwal *et al*⁵ has reported the application of 2-hydroxy-4-sulphodiazonaphthalene as an adsorption indicator in argentometric titrations.

In the present communication, the results of the studies on the application of 7-hydroxy-8 (phenyl azo) naphthalene 1,3-disulphonic acid (orange G) as adsorption indicator in the argentometric determinations of some halides and pseudohalides such as chloride, bromide, iodide and thiocyanate has been described and discussed.

Experimental

Materials : All the chemicals used were of AR BDH or GR (E. Merck) grade. The stock solutions of alkali halides, thiocyanate and silver nitrate were prepared and standardised by usual methods.

The dye 'orange G' was used in the form of 0.1% solution in double distilled water. The solution was kept in a stoppered container.

Instrument : The pH measurements were recorded with the help of precision pH-meter (PR 9405 M) with an accuracy ± 0.02 pH units, using standard glass (PV 9011) and calomel (PV 9021) electrodes.

Methods : In the argentometry of halides (Cl^- , Br^- , I^-) and pseudohalide (SCN^-), the 'orange G' dye is found to exhibit a sharp color change from yellow to pink in the pH range 2-6. The indicator responds equally well in the reverse titration (Ag^+ versus halides) with a color change from pink to yellow at the equivalence point.

10.00 ml of halide or thiocyanate solution were taken and the pH of the solution was adjusted in the pH range 2-6. 2 to 3 drops of dye solution were added to the solution which was titrated against standard silver nitrate solution. The coagulation of AgX or AgSCN ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , I^-) started just before the equivalence point at which the precipitate acquired a pink color. The reverse titrations could also be carried out satisfactorily indicating

color change from pink to yellow at the equivalence point. The results are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

Determination of iodide and bromide in a binary mixture : Since chloride, bromide and iodide can be quantitatively titrated argentometrically using

TABLE 1—'ORANGE G' AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR IN ARGENTOMETRIC TITRATION OF HALIDE/THIOCYANATE IONS

Volume of K-halides/thiocyanate titrated = 10.00 ml		
Conc. of halide/thiocyanate	Volume and conc. of silver nitrate	Detailed conditions
0.1M KCl/KSCN	9.95-10.00 ml of 0.1M AgNO_3	The titration was performed in presence of 1.5-3.0 ml of 0.01M HNO_3 . The color change (yellow to pink) was sharp and reversible and coagulation of Ag-halide/thiocyanate occurred just before the end point. The titration was performed in presence of 1.5-3.5 ml of 0.01M HNO_3 . Coagulation occurred at the eqvt. point. The color change was not as sharp as in above.
0.1M KBr/KI	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.1M AgNO_3	
0.02M KCl/KSCN	10.00 ml of 0.02M AgNO_3	
0.02M KBr	9.95-10.00 ml of 0.02M AgNO_3	
0.02M KI	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.02M AgNO_3	
0.01M KCl/KBr	9.95-10.00 ml of 0.01M AgNO_3	
0.01M KI/KSCN	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.01M AgNO_3	
0.005M KCl/KI	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.005M AgNO_3	
0.005M KBr/KSCN	10.00 ml of 0.005M AgNO_3	

TABLE 2—'ORANGE G' AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR IN THE TITRATION OF Ag^+ IONS WITH HALIDE OR THIOCYANATE

Volume of AgNO_3 titrated = 10.00 ml		
Conc. of AgNO_3	Volume and conc. of thiocyanate/halide	Detailed conditions
0.1M AgNO_3	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.1M KCl/KSCN	The titration was performed in presence of 1.5-2.0 ml of 0.01M HNO_3 . Coagulation of Ag-halide/thiocyanate occurred earlier and dye adsorbed on the coagulated precipitate, but at equiv. point desorption of the dye begins. Changes are sharp and reversible.
0.1M AgNO_3	10.00 ml of 0.1M KBr/KI	
0.02M AgNO_3	9.95-10.00 ml of 0.02M KCl/KBr/KI	
0.02M AgNO_3	10.00 ml of 0.02M KSCN	
0.01M AgNO_3	10.00-10.05 ml of 0.01M KCl/KI	
0.01M AgNO_3	9.95-10.00 ml of 0.01M KBr/KSCN	

7-hydroxy-8 (phenyl azo) naphthalene 1,3-disulphonic acid (orange G) as adsorption indicator in pH range 2-6, the determination of any of these halides in presence of each other, was not possible. However, chloride or bromide in presence of iodide can be estimated by the following procedures⁶.

- (i) Total halide (Cl^- or Br^- and I^-) contents of a suitable aliquot of solution can be titrated against silver nitrate in the pH range 2-6.
- (ii) A separate similar aliquot of the solution containing the mixed halide (i) is acidified with dilute HNO_3 and boiled with slight excess of NaNO_2 to decompose iodide and expel out iodine completely. The remaining chloride or bromide can then be titrated accurately by the procedure given earlier.
- (iii) The difference of the two titre values corresponds to the amount of iodide present in the solution of the binary mixture. The results of such analysis are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—TITRATION OF I^- AND Br^- WITH AgNO_3 TAKING 7-HYDROXY-8 (PHENYL AZO) NAPHTHALENE 1,3-DISULPHONIC ACID AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR

Volume of 0.1M solution taken		Volume of 0.1M AgNO_3 required	
KI	KBr	First titration	Second titration
9.00 ml	1.00 ml	10.00-10.05 ml	1.00-0.95 ml
8.00 ml	2.00 ml	10.00-10.05 ml	2.00-1.95 ml
7.00 ml	3.00 ml	10.00-10.05 ml	3.00-2.95 ml
6.00 ml	4.00 ml	10.00-10.05 ml	4.00-3.95 ml
5.00 ml	5.00 ml	10.00-10.05 ml	5.00-4.95 ml
4.00 ml	6.00 ml	9.95-10.00 ml	5.95-6.00 ml
3.00 ml	7.00 ml	9.95-10.00 ml	6.95-7.00 ml
2.00 ml	8.00 ml	9.95-10.00 ml	8.00-8.05 ml
1.00 ml	9.00 ml	10.00-10.05 ml	9.00-9.05 ml

Preparation of Ag-dye complex : 0.3 gm of dye was dissolved in the least amount of water. The solution was made slightly ammoniacal. On adding 20% AgNO_3 solution to this, a red silver dye compound was precipitated out, which was filtered and washed to free it from dye. Dark red compound was left for few hours in a desiccator. It was sparingly soluble in water. The Ag-dye compound was analysed for silver in duplicate. The following

structure may be proposed to Ag-dye compound on the basis of Ag content found in the compound (experimental: Ag % 33.32/33.80; calculated for the formula, 33.70).

Discussion

7-Hydroxy-8 (phenyl azo) naphthalene 1,3-disulphonic acid imparts a pink color to the silver halide precipitate in the pH range 2-6, due to the surface adsorption in the argentometric titrations of halide and thiocyanate ions. The color development at the surface of AgX precipitate may be attributed to the formation of Ag-dye complex just near the equivalence point in presence of a slight excess of Ag^+ . Because of high solubility product of Ag-dye complex its adsorption on the surface occurs giving a color change at the end-point.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. J. P. Tandon, Rajasthan University, Jaipur and to Dr. R. C. Sharma, Lecturer in Chemistry, Agra College, Agra for their valuable suggestions during this work. Thanks are also due to Dr. S. M. L. Gupta, Head of the Chemistry Department, Agra College, Agra for providing laboratory facilities and CSIR, New Delhi for awarding a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (S. K. G.).

References

1. R. C. MEHROTRA, R. D. TEWARI and H. L. DUBEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **24**, 165.
2. I. M. KOLTHOFF, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1927, **70**, 395.
3. K. N. TANDON and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, **27**, 97.
4. E. SINGH and R. W. NATHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 864.
5. D. C. AGARWAL and G. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 145.
6. P. S. DUBEY, Ph.D. Thesis, Agra Univ. (1969).